

COMPETITIVE ANXIETY LEVEL BEFORE AND DURING COMPETITION OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL KURASH ATHLETES**Samandarov A.****Ergasheva M.***Retraining and Qualification Institute on Physical Education and Sports,
Samarkand branch, Samarkand State University***Abstract**

The trouble and anxiety of an athlete in the process of participating in competitions and in the process of competitions is the main obstacle to achieving sports results. Nevertheless, the type of sport, kurash received a competition, and the psychological state of the continuation of the competition, in particular, the problem of trouble and anxiety, has not been scientifically studied. The purpose of this article is to investigate the state of trouble and anxiety during the competition, as well as to determine the difference between the state of trouble during the competition and the state of anxiety during the competition. A total of 450 kurash athletes voluntarily participated in the research work (high/international level) (225), kurash athletes of national categories (university/national level) (225), males 238, females 212). The research works and verification of participants were carried out in 4 major competitions on the territory of Uzbekistan. The instrument used for the research was the Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 which consisted of 27 items and tested twice: before and during the match to examine level of anxiety prior and during the competition. To test the research hypotheses the t-test was used and P values were set at $p < 0.05$ for all measures. The obtained results showed that the participants of the competition received an average ventilation condition of 45.5783 for male kurash athletes and 46.6532 for female kurash athletes. (t -test-6.506, $p < 0.05$). In addition, the international level kurash athletes of the competition received a state of anxiety, which amounted to 39,3590, while the national category kurash athletes had a state of 44,0218 ($F=14.110$, $p < 0.05$). The study also revealed that the level of trouble and anxiety of international kurash athletes (38,6400) during the competition was lower than that of national kurash athletes (43,8439) ($F=7.899$, $p < 0.05$). The results of the study indicate the need to optimize the psychological training that kurash athletes of the national category received from competitions, as well as the organization of training with females on the basis of a separate approach, in particular, the implementation of psychological training.

Keywords: kurash, anxiety, before competition, during competition, gender, level.

Introduction

Many psychologists argue that the state of psychological anxiety and fear of an athlete, which took the competition, negatively affects the results in sports (Cox, 1990; Martens et al., 1990; Wiggins, 1998). For this reason, in the field of sports psychology, an athlete received a competition, and the study of the problem of optimizing the psychological state during the continuation of competitions has not lost its scientific significance and relevance. It is important to note that this problem has received a low level of competition, as noted in new and recent studies on the scientific front of modern sports anxiety (competitive anxiety), and the state of panic in competition (arousal) positively affects the achievement of directly high results (Won & Oh, 2019; Silva et al., 2019; Dimiyati & Ria, 2020).

Kurash is a sport based on individual combat, only in 1998 it was officially recognized as a sport and the International Kurash Association (IKA) was established (Yusupov, 2005). Currently, there are more than 130 national kurash federations around the world. Kurash was included in the program of the Asian Games in 2018 in Jakarta, Indonesia. According to a number of authors, the further development of the kurash and its inclusion in the Olympic Games program are directly related to research work, and in this regard, there is not enough research work (Khaitov et al., 2020). In particular, kurash athletes received a competition, and the issue of scientific study of the

psychological state of the competitive process has not yet found its solution.

It is known from the results of modern sports practice and experience that athletes of different levels and categories anxiety before and during the competition was determined as different (Hanton, 2003; Mehran & Hassan, 2009). The researchers also identify some psychological circumstances in both team and individual sports, in particular, a specific differentiation of motivation (Moradi et al., 2020). In this regard, the results of the study conducted by the Males and Kerr show that in the event of an approaching competition in the desired sport, the state of anxiety that engulfed the participants of the competition be sharply higher (Males & Kerr, 1996). In another research paper, it was noted that the competition took place, and it was determined that the level of ventilation during the competition further increase the likelihood that the athlete will have a stroke (Covassin et al., 2015). It is important to note that in the most recent studies, the psychological state of the competitive process, motivation and behavior have a certain impact on the competitive position of an athlete, such as significant achievements (Jachec, 2021).

An analysis of a number of literature has shown that the kurash competition took place, and an adequate scientific study of the problem of scientific research of the state of anxiety during the competition is not abstract. For this reason, the purpose of this article is to (1) investigate the state of kurash athletes during the competition and (2) determine the difference between

the state of kurash athletes during the competition and the state of kurash athletes at different levels and bodies.

Methods

Participants

In total, 450 wrestlers took part in this research work, including highly qualified kurash athletes (high/international level) (225), kurash athletes of the national category (university/national level) (225). The ratio of participants by gender, males 238, females 212.

Procedure

Data on the participants of the study and verification of participants were conducted in 4 major competitions on the territory of Uzbekistan (Jizzakh, the Championship of Uzbekistan, Bukhara, the Championship of Uzbekistan, Chirchik, the Cup of Uzbekistan, Universiade, Competitions between university students).

Inclusion criteria: The participants 16-25 years old; training experience more than 4 years, male and female kurash athletes.

Exclusion criteria: Refusal to participate in the study; any acute or chronic condition that would limit the ability of the athletes to participate in the study.

Ethical Considerations

The Local Ethical Committee of the Samarkand State University (Protocol number N4323-10, 02.11.2018) approved the research procedures. No interferences were made in the nutritional, or hydration status of participants. Before the experiment, participants attended a briefing meeting and signed an informed consent document to measure that they understood the testing procedures and the risks and benefits

associated with the study. The local Ethics and Research Committee, following the WMA's Declaration of Helsinki, previously approved this research.

Assessment

The instrument used for the research was the Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 which consisted of 27 items. The CSAI-2 included both the cognitive and somatic aspects. The CSAI-2 test was tested twice: before and during the match to examine level of anxiety prior and during the competition. The data were analysed by SPSS for Windows and the expressed as mean and standard deviation. To test the research hypotheses the t-test was used and P values were set at $p < 0.05$ for all measures.

Results

Gender differences

As described in Table 1, the competition took place, and the state of anxiety during the competition is relatively low for males than for females kurash athletes. In particular, the competitions received a state of anxiety, on average 45,5783 for males and 46,6532 for females kurash athletes. The level of trouble and anxiety experienced by the participants of the competitions with different descriptions was higher than that of male and female kurash athletes, and there was a statistical difference between the results (t-test-6.506, $p < 0.05$). It was also found that the level of trouble and anxiety during the competition was significantly lower in men than in females kurash athletes. In particular, the state of trouble and anxiety during the competition was equal to 42.6268 for males and 45.4821 for females kurash athletes. Comparably, even during the competition, males were distinguished by a low level of air conditioning compared to female kurash athletes (t-test-5.5839, $p < 0.05$).

Table 1

Competitive Anxiety Level of kurash athletes by gender categories

Level of competitive anxiety	Gender	Before competition			During competition		
		Mean	t-test	p-value	Mean	t-test	p-value
	Female	46.6532	6.506*	0.001	45.4821	5.839	0.000*
Male	45.5783	42.6268					

*Notes: $p < 0.05$
Sport Level

Kurash athletes of international and national levels took part in the competition, and the state of trouble and anxiety during the competition is described in Table 2. The obtained results confirmed that the kurash athletes of the international level received the competition and that the state and level of anxiety during the competition were at a lower level than that of the kurash athletes of the national category. In particular, it hosted competitions among kurash athletes of the international level, while the state of anxiety was 39,3590, which was 44,0218 for kurash athletes of the national

category. There was a statistical difference between the results ($F=14.110$, $p < 0.05$). In the course of the study, it was also confirmed that the level of trouble and anxiety in the competitive process is also high in athletes of the national category. According to the results of the study, it was found that the level of trouble and anxiety in the competitive process among international kurash athletes (38,6400), respectively, was lower than that of national kurash athletes (43,8439). A statistical difference was found between the results ($F=7.899$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 2

Competitive Anxiety Level of kurash athletes based on the athletic level

Athletes' Level	Before competition			During competition		
	Mean	F-value	p-value	Mean	F-value	p-value
International	39.3590	14.110	0.001*	38.6400	7.899	0.001*
National	44.0218			43.8439		

*Notes: $p < 0.05$

Discussion

Gender

The results obtained during the study confirmed that female kurash athletes received competitions, and the state of trouble and anxiety during the competition is higher than that of male participants. Our observations and the results of the experiment fully confirmed the results of the research of a number of scientists and researchers. The research work of the researchers showed that, unlike the sport and the qualification of an athlete, the state of anxiety in female athletes and competitors who received air conditioning is at a higher level than in males (Scanlan & Passer, 1979; Kessler et al., 1994; Cartoni et al., 2005). It is important to note that the results of a recent study conducted by scientists showed that there is no difference between the level of trouble and anxiety experienced by female and male athletes participating in competitions (Aksoy et al., 2016). Correia & Rosado noted that the level of trouble and anxiety experienced by the participants of the competition is directly related to the type of sports found, the level of anxiety experienced by the participants of the competition in solo sports is higher than in team sports (Correia & Rosado, 2019).

It is important that a number of scientists took part in the competition and noted that the level of trouble and anxiety during the competition is directly related to biological factors. The results of the study generally showed that females who took part in the competition confirmed that the level of trouble and anxiety was higher than that of males (Montgomery & Moris, 1994; Lewinsohn et al., 1998). In addition, other researchers claim that the state of trouble and anxiety that competition has picked up is directly related to social outbursts (Jones & Cale, 1989). In our opinion, this issue is multifactorial, and there is a need for in-depth scientific research and studies. Because until now, there has not been a sufficient number of research works on wrestling, and the scientific basis of this sport is practically not studied.

Sport Level

The results of our study confirmed that athletes at the international level took part in competitions, and that the level of trouble and anxiety during the competition is low, on the contrary, the state of trouble and anxiety is high for kurash athletes of the national category. These results obtained in the course of research are fully confirmed by the results of the research work of many scientists (Martens et al., 1990; Cox, 2007; Lu et al., 2010; Dhanda, 2019; Frame & Reichin, 2019). In other words, a high level of skill is characterized not only by technical and tactical or physical training, but also by mental stability, which was adopted by the competition. According to Bompa's noted, in the preparation of an athlete, a holistic training is important, which is the main achievement of victory in the competition process. Also, when preparing an athlete for competitions, the importance of comprehensive training should be taken into account (Bompa et al., 2019).

Conclusion

There are also certain shortcomings in this research work. In particular, the study did not study the psychological state of the kurash athletes after the

competition. Also, kurash athletes received a competition, and the psychological state of the competitive process and its connection with hormonal failures were not investigated.

The results of this study confirmed that when competing at the national level, the resulting state of trouble and anxiety would be higher than that of international-class kurash athletes. This, in turn, indicates the need to optimize the psychological training of kurash athletes of the national category who took part in competitions. The trouble and anxiety during the competition has caused which can become a serious obstacle for kurash athletes of the national category.

In addition, the same thing was found again in the course of the study, since female kurash athletes also took part in competitions and as long as the state of anxiety during the competition was high. These results indicate the need to organize training directly with females on the basis of a separate approach, in particular, for conducting psychological training.

Future researches

To date, no in-depth studies and studies have been conducted on kurash. In the future, it is worth studying the relationship between psychological readiness and the level of technical and tactical skill of kurash athletes, as well as the problem of hormonal changes in the psychological state that took the competition.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Martens, R., Vealey, R. S., & Burton, D. (1990). Competitive anxiety in sport.
2. Cox, R. (1990). Sport psychology: concepts and applications.
3. Wiggins, M. (1998). Anxiety intensity and direction: Preperformance temporal patterns and expectations in athletes. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 10, 201-211.
4. Won, S., & Oh, S. (2019). The Structural Relationship between Perfectionism, Stress, and Competitive Anxiety of Taekwondo Student-Athletes.
5. Dimiyati, Djoko P.I., Ria L. (2020), *Exploring the Psychological Skills of Indonesian Penchak Silat Athletes at the 18th Asian Games*, "Ido Movement for Culture. Journal of Martial Arts Anthropology", vol. 20, no.2, pp. 10-16. doi: 10.14589/ido.20.2.2.
6. Silva, G.C., Cortez, A.C., Júnior, J.R., Granja, C.T., Conde, E., & Melo, G.F. (2019). Analysis of pre-competitive anxiety of Brazilian young swimmers. *Acta Scientiarum. Health Science*, 41, 45475.
7. Yusupov, K. (2005), *International Kurash rules, technique and tactics*, Tashkent., "Gafur Gulom", pp. 132. [in Uzbek].
8. Khaitov O., Abdulakhatov A., Norboyev K., Kulbulov F., Azamkhonov O., Ahmedov F. (2020), *Kurash: history, theory and methodics*, Monograph, Shawnee, USA; pp. 52; DOI.10.37057/M_9.

9. АХМЕДОВ, Ф. (2020). МУСОБАҚА ОЛДИ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИНГ ДЗЮДОЧИЛАР ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИГА ТАЪСИРИ. *Фан-Спортга*, (4), 76-78

10. Hanton, S., O'Brien, M., & Mellalieu, S. (2003). Individual differences, perceived control and competitive trait anxiety. *Journal of sport behavior*, 26, 39-55.

11. Mehran, S., & Hassan, A. (2009). The role of cognitive and somatic anxiety in athletic performance.

12. Moradi, J., Bahrami, A. & Dana, A. (2020). Motivation for Participation in Sports Based on Athletes in Team and Individual Sports. *Physical Culture and Sport. Studies and Research*, 85(1) 14-21. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pccsr-2020-0002>

13. Males, J.R., & Kerr, J. (1996). Stress, Emotion, and Performance in Elite Slalom Canoeists. *Sport Psychologist*, 10, 17-36.

14. Covassin, T., Beidler, E., Ostrowski, J., Wallace, J. (2015), *Psychosocial aspects of rehabilitation in sports*, "Clinics in sports medicine", vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 199-212; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csm.2014.12.004>

15. Jachec, T. (2021). Competitive spirit as a form of behavioral addiction: the case study of Michael Jordan. *Physical Culture and Sport. Studies and Research*, 89(1) 66-83. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pccsr-2021-0007>.

16. Hayitov, O., & Akhmedov, F. (2018). CLASSIFICATION OF TECHNICAL MOVEMENTS OF KURASH. Current problems of theory and practice of physical culture, sport and tourism (pp. 686-689).

DIDACTIC ADVANTAGES OF USING INFORMATION ON INTERNET RESOURCES IN THE LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract

The article discusses the use of Internet resources in the learning process. They provide basic information about the use of the Internet, define this textbook, consider its advantages and confirm the relevance of their use in teaching foreign languages. The article is intended for those who are interested in public reading and creating a favorable environment for learning.

Keywords: information technologies 1, Internet resources 2, didactic tasks 3, learning process 4, the Internet 5, high-quality language education 6.

Nowadays, the Internet has become an integral part of the life of a modern person. Mail, telephony and business are moving to the Internet. There are more and more sources of information on the web. The number of network users and the number of information pages is constantly growing. For most young people, the Internet is becoming a familiar and convenient means of communication and information. Students actively use the Internet. 9 out of 10 students use e-mail every day, search the Internet for news, information, work. The Internet is primarily an information network. The presence of a huge amount of materials on the Web and specialized search engines makes the Internet an indispensable tool for finding information in the learning process, both for the teacher and the student.

And we can say that now there is no doubt about the relevance of integrating the Internet into the learning process. At the same time, the main subject of discussion is not the question of why, but how to apply modern computer technologies in the learning process. The use of the Internet would significantly expand the range of real communicative situations, increase the motivation of students, and would allow them to apply the acquired knowledge, skills, and speech skills to solve real communicative problems.

The need to use Internet resources in the educational process in the modern world is due to the following factors:

- fast and cheap access to the necessary information;
- the ability to communicate (Skype, e-mail) with groupmates on educational issues, as well as the ability to contact the teacher;
- access to research and statistical information in preparation for classes (facilitating the implementation of tasks);
- the ability to access encyclopedic information at any time (including photo and video information);
- accessible news search (including economic, legal news, historical reports, speeches of public figures, biographies);
- online distance learning.[1]

If for students the main advantage of using the global network is a convenient, affordable and easy way to find the necessary information, then for teachers the following main advantages of using Internet resources can be distinguished:

- quick search for educational materials for classes;
- the ability to quickly access the regulatory framework;